

THE PERCEIVED SERVANT LEADERSHIP STYLE OF MANUFACTURING COMPANY Z IN MANAGING EMPLOYEE PERFORMANCE

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ABSTRACT

This study examined the level of perceived servant leadership dimensions such as love, service, empowerment, trust, and altruism on the employee performance of Company Z. A quantitative research method was used on a sample of 250 regular employees from various departments for Company Z. A structured Likert scale questionnaire consists of several statements measuring scales was used and administered to the respondents. A follow-up questionnaire for key informant interviews was done to support the proposed programs that Company Z may adopt in managing employee performance and turnover. The data were analyzed using descriptive statistics (mean), Cronbach's alpha (reliability), and Spearman correlation for testing the hypothesis. The results of descriptive analysis on the servant leadership variable exhibited that generally, respondents agreed that the dimensions of servant leadership influenced their performance. Specifically, the higher the mean, the more employees perceived that their leaders foster servant leadership style and made them feel empowered and eager to perform and deliver what is expected of them at work. Furthermore, the results of Spearman correlation through hypothesis testing revealed that servant leadership dimensions: love, service, empowerment, trust, and altruism had a low to moderate significant relationship with employee performance. Given the overall results, the researcher recommends that the programs or policies formulated be adopted by Company Z; conduct a study that focuses on how leaders perceived themselves as a servant leader and cover other dimensions or mediators as predictor variables for more extensive findings.

Keywords: *Servant Leadership, Love, Service, Empowerment, Trust, Altruism, and Employee Performance*

INTRODUCTION

Leadership plays a vital role in managing the people and the organization. Managers or leaders are responsible for ensuring the team's success, creating a positive and conducive environment, and solving complex problems while still encouraging employees to participate. However, once these responsibilities of leaders have been neglected and have drawn their attention away from the team members, then it can lead to a drop in productivity (Wilde, 2019), particularly in today's world that is constantly changing with a volatile, uncertain, complex, and ambiguous (VUCA) environment wherein things seem hard to understand and become unpredictable. It is important that today's leaders have the capability and willingness to serve their people while contributing not only to the success of the organization, but also to empowering employees toward growth.

In addition, managing employee performance is an organizational effort to assist employees in achieving their goals in the context of increasing performance contributions to the organization especially in times of challenges or crisis. Managing performance requires quality management because quality management practices had a positive impact on quality performance (Sundar and Prabhu, 2019). Singh et al. (2019) revealed that top management support, workforce commitment, people management, and workplace organization are directly related to organizational (business) performance. One of the aspects of organizational management that plays an essential role in this process is the practice of organizational leadership. It is the key to organizational success since the leader is the entity that influences the performance of subordinates to achieve organizational goals. Leadership style influences the total quality management of an organization (Hermanto and Srimulyani, 2022) Further, many studies proved that leadership styles have an implication not only for organizational performance, but also for employees or individual performance. One of which is the study of Muzira et.al. (2020) which shows how servant leadership promotes team spirit; if workers know that their leaders care for their needs, they get a sense of belongingness that motivates them to work even more and produce high performance.

Research Objectives

This research aimed to determine the perceived level of the servant leadership style of Company Z in terms of the following dimensions such as love, service, empowerment, trust, and altruism; to evaluate the relationship between servant leadership dimensions and employee performance and to propose programs that will help Company Z in managing employee performance and turnover.

Research Framework

Servant leaders create a positive working environment which leads to increased employee engagement, active participation at work, and most importantly a higher level of performance (Karl & Jon 2016). For this study, figure 1 showed the independent and dependent variables which helped the researcher analyze and organize the results of the study. Anchored this study with the social exchange theory, the researcher assessed the impact of dimensions of servant leadership such as love, altruism, empowerment, trust, and service towards employee performance of Company Z. These dimensions of servant leadership may be used as a tool to offer to the whole organization in order to address turnover and manage employee performance towards achieving the organizational goals.

Figure 1. Conceptual Framework

Significance of the Study

The results of the study will be of great benefit to the following:

Theory

This research assessed the suitability of the Social Exchange Theory that was developed by George Homans in 1958 which explains how social interactions are determined by the benefits of service exchange or reciprocity (Tulane University, 2018). This research will help reveal the significance of this theory in unleashing the covert behavior of employees in delivering their performance at work. Also, to evaluate whether the servant leadership style of Company Z may affect how employees react or perform

using these dimensions: love, service, empowerment, trust, and altruism. It is said that people used to look at the potential reward before engaging in any activities or endeavor, hence, the result of this study may construe how leaders influence the employee's behavior or performance. Therefore, when employees display positive behavior or performance at work, the more satisfaction employees are getting from the company or their leaders.

Policy

This research will be beneficial to Company Z in its quest to increase employee performance and increase retention in the organization. While evaluating the dimensions of servant leadership, the management of Company Z may formulate programs to upskill and train its set of officers on how to be genuine servant leaders which is timely and useful in this time of uncertainty or crisis (Walker, 2020). The company may use the results of this study to influence and motivate the roster of officers to jump and adopt this leadership style which will help them realize how valuable and influential a management style is in delivering success to the individual and organizational goals.

Practice

With the results of this study, company Z may be able to attain its desired outcomes wherein employees will be encouraged to imbibe ownership and motivate to perform their duties without anyone coercing or forcing them to perform. This study will enlighten companies that are ready to take on the challenge of delivering performance by grooming their officers to be servant leaders. Also, to focus on hiring and developing leaders that possess better qualities of serving others and give value in cultivating employees' potential. Managers may establish a conducive and supportive environment promoting empowerment, learning opportunities, and personal development of employees which contributes to their level of engagement and performance. In this environment, managers can encourage their employees to learn through mistakes, practice blameless culture, and enhance their relationships with employees to influence organizational performance.

Social Action

This research study may be of use to some researchers or companies in their intentions to improve employee performance, provide empowerment, and alleviate the level of attrition by establishing policies, plans, and programs relevant to this study's results.

Scope and Limitation

This research study focused on examining the impact of servant leadership on the employee performance of Company Z. This study focused only on the five dimensions

of servant leadership such as love, service, empowerment, trust, and altruism to evaluate how these dimensions affect the employee's performance in Company Z. The researcher used quantitative research to analyze the data that were gathered in this study. The respondents for this study were the 250 regular employees randomly selected from various departments and divisions of Company Z to acquire their perspectives. The conduct of this study in Company Z limits the generalizability of the results as it focused only on the employee's perspective as to how they see their leaders observe the servant leadership behavior and cannot be generalized for other Japanese manufacturing companies.

Definition of Terms

The following terms were operationally defined as used in the study.

Altruism. This refers to a behavior of prioritizing and giving focus to other people's needs.

Employee Empowerment. This refers to the way how companies or management provide their employees with autonomy, opportunity, and motivation to contribute to decision-making activities.

Employee Engagement. This refers to the feeling of involvement and enthusiasm of employees towards their work and workplace.

Employee Performance. This refers to how employees behave and fulfill their assigned tasks or expectations in the workplace.

Employee Turnover. This refers to the total number or percentage of employees leaving the company in a certain period.

Leadership. This refers to the action of leading a group of people or an organization toward achieving individual and organizational goals.

Love. This refers to a genuine concern of the leaders to their employees in delivering and supporting their needs in the organization.

Organizational Commitment. This refers to the level of engagement and dedication team members feel toward their jobs and the organization.

Organizational Performance. This refers to the ability of the organization to achieve goals set forth by the management in a specific period.

Servant Leadership. This refers to serving others first and helping them to attain their maximum potential.

Review of Related Literature

As cited in the study of Liao and Zhu (2020), Greenleaf coined the term servant leadership in 1970 and believes that it is a leadership style that prioritizes other people's needs and emphasizes "serving others" and the interests of the employee. Servant leadership is anchored in the human drive to bond with others and contribute to the betterment of society (Almutairi et al. 2020). An emphasis on service motivation, as demonstrated by empowering and developing employees with empathy and humility, differentiates servant leadership from other leadership frameworks (Harwiki, 2016). Kiker, Callahan, and Kiker (2019) indicated that servant leaders increase team potency and team effectiveness as servant leaders enhance the organization's goals. Servant leaders believe that it is their responsibility to assist others in learning and growing, feeling meaningful, inspired, energized, empowered, and contributing at their maximum level. People are encouraged to conduct good work that brings out the best in them when they are under the direction of servant leadership. Instead of teaching them how to do a better job, leaders are more likely to engage them by asking them how they can assist them in doing their jobs better. Leaders put the needs of their people ahead of their own. Establishing a supportive work atmosphere where employees feel valued and respected is a significant feature of servant leadership. Servant leadership can help create a more constructive professional atmosphere with a high level of enthusiasm and dedication. Businesses may develop, and workers can feel empowered if they show compassion, empathy, humility, and service. This, in turn, allows for more significant firm development (Khan et al., 2022b)

Farrington and Lillah (2019) studied the relationship between servant leadership and job satisfaction among healthcare workers. The findings showed a positive correlation between servant leadership and job satisfaction. In addition, Lee et al. (2018) also shared a positive correlation between the two constructs. Consequently, in every sector that researchers studied, the findings almost always showed a positive correlation between servant leadership and job satisfaction. Thus, these findings simply suggest that the application of servant leadership has a positive organizational outcome and improved job satisfaction among the employees working in the organization.

Here is the study by Bienkowska, et al. (2022) which showed the significance of servant leadership in influencing job performance. It is found that there is a direct relationship between servant leadership and employee turnover, where servant leadership supports the willingness of an employee to stay in the organization. A servant leader creates positive conditions for employee development and ensures employee autonomy, contributing to employee retention. There is also a relationship between servant leadership and job performance, which shows that a supporting leader can strengthen employee job performance. Furthermore, there is a direct relationship between employee turnover and job performance. The same results from the studies of Thakur and Verma (2020), Deconinck et al., (2017), Ng and Choi et al., (2016) also proved that servant leadership has a direct influence on the employee performance as well as the intention to leave the workplace. Therefore, if an employee is determined to leave the organization, their job performance is lower, and if the intention to stay in the organization is strong, their job performance is high.

METHODOLOGY

Research Design

A quantitative research design was selected in this study to determine the perceived level of servant leadership dimensions such as love, altruism, empowerment, trust, and service on employee performance. The response of the employees was measured through a validated survey questionnaire with a five-point Likert scale developed by the researcher. This survey questionnaire was the main tool for data collection and was distributed manually and online to investigate the impact of servant leadership dimensions on employee performance. The researcher sought expert advice from professionals to ensure the validity and reliability of the questionnaire.

Research Locale

The study was conducted in a Japanese manufacturing company engaged in the assembly and distribution of quality trucks, buses, and spare parts located at Laguna. In this research study, the researcher would be able to give aid to the challenges of company Z in managing employee performance and addressing its issues in turnover rate which impacted the operations and entails higher costs in hiring and training new employees onboard.

Population and Sampling Design

Company Z is a medium-sized manufacturing company; however, the focus of this research study was the 250 regular employees from various departments who had been with the company during the introduction of leadership training in 2018 up to 2021 implementation. The sampling design used was proportionate stratified sampling with employee category as a stratification variable (Manager, Supervisor, Rank & File), and the sample respondents for each employee category were determined by their number relative to the population.

Research Instrument

The data in the study were collected through a survey questionnaire with a 5-point Likert scale (1-Strongly Disagree, 2-Disagree, 3-Neutral, 4-Agree, 5-Strongly Agree). This survey questionnaire was a combination of self-constructed and modified statements generated from literature reviews which were tested by professionals to ensure validity and reliability.

Data Gathering Procedure

A 5-point Likert scale questionnaire was used in gathering the quantitative data for this research. Also, a key informant interview was facilitated with the selected employees to validate and support the results of this study. The data gathered were tabulated and analyzed to support and answer the research questions.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

This study revealed that the dimensions of servant leadership such as love, service, empowerment, trust, and altruism had an impact on employees' performance. Generally, all respondents conveyed their agreement on the impact of servant leadership on their performance. All these dimensions showed an acceptable weighted mean and were described as "Agree" with the following items: love (3.93), service (3.94), empowerment (4.12), trust (3.97), and altruism (3.92). As shown, empowerment received the highest weighted mean from the respondents while altruism had the lowest.

Table 1. Mean Ratings of Love on the Perceived Level Servant Leadership on Employee Performance

Indicators	Weighted Mean	Interpretation
1. My superior is genuinely interested in me as a person	3.82	Agree
2. My superior shows care/ concern for me through encouragement and affirmation.	3.98	Agree
3. My Superior shows compassion in his/her actions towards me.	3.95	Agree
4. My Superior accepts and appreciates me and my flaws as his/her member.	3.96	Agree
Overall Weighted Mean	3.93	Agree

Scale: Strongly Agree – 4.51 to 5.00, Agree – 3.51 to 4.50, Neutral – 2.51 to 3.50, Disagree – 1.51 to 2.50, Strongly Disagree – 1.00-1.50

Table 1 presents the respondents' assessment on the level of impact of servant leadership dimensions on employee performance using weighted mean. Generally, the respondents agreed on all the items that pertain to love as a dimension of servant leadership with an overall weighted mean of 3.93. Specifically, the statement "My superior shows care/ concern for me through encouragement and affirmation" received the highest agreement level among the respondents with a weighted mean of 3.98. Meanwhile, the statement "My superior is genuinely interested in me as a person" obtained the lowest agreement level among the respondents with a weighted mean of 3.82.

Table 2. Mean Ratings of Service on the Perceived Level of Servant Leadership on Employee Performance

Indicators	Weighted Mean	Interpretation
1. My Superior makes my career development a priority.	3.86	Agree
2. My Superior is interested in making sure that I reach my career goals.	3.92	Agree
3. My Superior provides me with work experiences that enable me to develop new skills.	4.02	Agree
4. My Superior wants to know about my career goals and aspirations.	3.96	Agree
Overall Weighted Mean	3.94	Agree

Scale: Strongly Agree – 4.51 to 5.00, Agree – 3.51 to 4.50, Neutral – 2.51 to 3.50, Disagree – 1.51 to 2.50, Strongly Disagree – 1.00-1.50

Table 2. shows that the statement “My Superior provides me with work experiences that enable me to develop new skills” had the highest weighted mean of 4.02 which described employee’s agreement with this statement. On the other hand, the statement “My Superior makes my career development a priority” received the lowest response rate with a weighted mean of 3.86. However, the results presented a total of 3.94 weighted mean which respondents agreed to all its contents.

Table 3. Mean Ratings of Empowerment on the Perceived Level of Servant Leadership on Employee Performance

Indicators	Weighted Mean	Interpretation
1. My Superior encourages me to handle important work decisions on my own.	4.12	Agree
2. My Superior gives me freedom to handle difficult situations in the way they feel is best.	4.19	Agree
3. My Superior offers me abundant opportunities to learn new skills and competencies.	4.06	Agree
4. My Superior encourages me to come up and suggest innovative ideas.	4.12	Agree
Overall Weighted Mean	4.12	Agree

Scale: Strongly Agree – 4.51 to 5.00, Agree – 3.51 to 4.50, Neutral – 2.51 to 3.50, Disagree – 1.51 to 2.50, Strongly Disagree – 1.00-1.50

Based on the results of the survey, respondents agreed on statements 1 and 4 “My Superior encourages me to handle important” and “My Superior encourages me to come up and suggest innovative ideas work decisions on my own” as both received a weighted mean of 4.12 which was the highest among the 4 statements. Meanwhile, the statement “My Superior offers me abundant opportunities to learn

new skills and competencies” got the lowest score or weighted mean of 4.06. However, in general, the results showed that employees agreed on empowerment as it received an overall weighted mean of 4.12.

Table 4. Mean Ratings of Trust on the Perceived Level of Servant Leadership on Employee Performance

Indicators	Weighted Mean	Interpretation
1. My manager shows his/her true feelings/emotions towards me and my team when giving performance feedback.	3.83	Agree
2. My Superior always communicates with me when there are work-related issues.	4.11	Agree
3. My Superior always makes time to talk to me on a personal level when he found out that I am struggling with my tasks.	3.86	Agree
4. My Superior honestly evaluates my performance in a fair and transparent manner.	4.08	Agree
Overall Weighted Mean	3.97	Agree

Scale: Strongly Agree – 4.51 to 5.00, Agree – 3.51 to 4.50, Neutral –2.51 to 3.50, Disagree – 1.51 to 2.50, Strongly Disagree – 1.00-1.50

For the trust, the employees believed that their superiors honestly evaluate their performance with a weighted mean of 4.08 which was the highest, while the lowest is 3.83 where they perceived that their managers show true feelings towards the team. Table 4 shows the overall mean results of 3.97 wherein employees convey their agreement.

Table 5. Mean Ratings of Altruism on the Perceived Level of Servant Leadership on the Employee Performance

Indicators	Weighted Mean	Interpretation
1. My Superior enjoys giving credit and celebrating the success of the team more than his own.	3.89	Agree
2. My Superior provides mentoring or coaching session even it affects his personal time to ensure that I grow professionally.	3.94	Agree
3. My Superior prioritizes my needs and my team ahead of his own.	3.80	Agree
4. My Superior always ask me of how he/she can be of help to ease or deliver my tasks rather than giving commands.	4.05	Agree
Overall Weighted Mean	3.92	Agree

Scale: Strongly Agree – 4.51 to 5.00, Agree – 3.51 to 4.50, Neutral –2.51 to 3.50, Disagree – 1.51 to 2.50, Strongly Disagree – 1.00-1.50

Results for mean ratings of altruism statements are demonstrated in Table 5. The results found that the employees agreed that their superiors always ask if they can help the team in delivering the tasks as it got 4.05 weighted mean while the statement “My Superior prioritizes my needs and my team ahead of his own” scored the lowest of 3.80 weighted mean. Overall, a weighted mean of 3.92 resulted from the agreements of all the respondents on the constructs of altruism.

Table 6. Mean Ratings of Individual/Employee Performance

Indicators	Weighted Mean	Interpretation
1. I can carry out my responsibilities effectively and efficiently.	4.42	Agree
2. I have mastered all phases of my job and the required skills to get everything delivered on time.	4.50	Agree
3. I execute my tasks with high regard for quality and productivity standards.	4.46	Agree
4. I am always open to new tasks and challenges even outside my scope.	4.46	Agree
Overall Weighted Mean	4.46	Agree

Scale: Strongly Agree – 4.51 to 5.00, Agree – 3.51 to 4.50, Neutral – 2.51 to 3.50, Disagree – 1.51 to 2.50, Strongly Disagree – 1.00-1.50

Table 6 presents the data that the employees agreed that they have mastered all phases of their jobs and are able to deliver on time which received the highest weighted mean of 4.50. On the other hand, employees who believed that they could carry out their responsibilities effectively and efficiently received the lowest weighted mean of 4.42. Generally, employees were all in agreement on this individual performance construct as it received an overall weighted mean of 4.46.

The next finding was supported and proven by the precedent literature that indeed servant leadership had a significant relationship with the employee’s performance as the data showed a low to moderate positive correlation; thus, rejected the Ho. This study found that there was a low to moderate correlation between the dimensions and employee performance. Specifically, altruism is moderately correlated with employee performance ($\rho=0.422$, $p<0.01$). Meanwhile, employee performance has a low correlation with love ($\rho=0.294$, $p<0.01$), service ($\rho=0.372$, $p<0.01$), empowerment ($\rho=0.390$, $p<0.01$), and trust ($\rho=0.349$, $p<0.01$).

Table 7. Spearman Correlation: Significant Relationship between the Servant Leadership Dimensions and Employee Performance

Servant Leadership Dimensions	Factor	Spearman Rho (ρ)	p-value	Strength of Association	Decision	Relationship
Love	Employee Performance	0.294	0.000	Low	Reject Ho	Significant
Service		0.372	0.000	Low	Reject Ho	Significant
Empowerment		0.390	0.000	Low	Reject Ho	Significant
Trust		0.349	0.000	Low	Reject Ho	Significant
Altruism		0.422	0.000	Moderate	Reject Ho	Significant

Note: Correlation is computed at 5% level of significance. If p-value is less than 0.05, there is a significant relationship, thus reject Ho. If otherwise, there is no significant relationship, therefore accept Ho.

Lastly, the following proposed programs were summarized by the researcher that Company Z may adopt in addressing its challenges like turnover and supporting its best practices that affect how employees perceived servant leadership in the company.

Proposed Program 1: Employee Development Ladder – This will help Company Z develop and enhance employees’ skills and competencies needed for their functions and succeed in current and future assignments; prioritizes the needs of its people by providing different employee development programs that will involve, engage, and empower them to perform at their best. Providing coaching or mentoring programs, continuous feedback, and recognition programs will boost employees’ motivation to do good and even stay longer in the company in return.

Proposed Program 2: Leaders and Values Transformation – Revisiting the vision, mission, and values of the Company may help the management align its leaders and people with the culture and values of Servant Leadership. This will also help create an environment that promotes recognition and culture of “malasakit” for all the resources of the organization.

Proposed Program 3: Total Rewards and Recognition Programs – Organizing a robust program for recognizing the efforts and contributions of employees will motivate them to deliver their best. Moreso, will create an avenue to recognize and honor employees who are dedicated to driving the overall success of the organization.

Conclusions

Based on the indicated findings, the following conclusions were drawn:

1. All the mean ratings calculated for each dimension of servant leadership showed “Agree” which means that respondents perceived that those dimensions had an impact on their performance. Although the result may be positive and favorable to Company Z, still the management must conduct other programs or interventions to instill the true essence of servant leadership among its leaders and pass it on to the employees as clearly supported by the data that servant leadership influenced employee’s performance.
2. The result of the study rejected the Ho and proved that all the dimensions included in the questionnaire on servant leadership had a low to moderate correlation with employee performance. It may seem to be good data to support that the company had shown and even practiced servant leadership, the Company Z still needs to work on improving the effectiveness of this leadership style in the organization. Company Z must help all its employees realize the importance of every dimension of servant leadership toward achieving individual and organizational performance.
3. The researcher formulated and proposed programs that Company Z may adopt in order to continue and improve the engagement of people in embracing servant leadership. Furthermore, Company Z should continue to empower and involve its people to ensure success in every area of the business as it is proven to be the highest weighted mean that drives employees to perform and deliver their best.

Recommendations

This study revealed that servant leadership had an impact on employee performance. Thus, the following recommendations are hereby presented:

1. The researcher suggests that Company Z may adopt the proposed programs formulated in this research to increase awareness and embrace the true meaning of servant leadership.
2. The study only focused on the employee’s perception of their leaders in practicing servant leadership in the organization. Although the results showed a significant correlation between servant leadership and employee performance, the researcher recommends that future researchers indulge and evaluate the leader’s perception of how they see themselves as servant leaders to strike a balance between the employee and leaders’ perception and ensure that programs to be introduced are aligned with the company goals.
3. This research focused only on the five (5) dimensions of servant leadership; thus, future researchers may also look for other possible dimensions and even impart some mediators such as employee engagement, organizational commitment,

and other factors that influence employee performance and keep employees empowered and involved.

Compliance with Ethical Standards

The researcher ensured compliance with the ethical standards such as the identity and anonymity of the respondents were not disclosed and were dealt with in strict confidentiality. All respondents were oriented regarding the objectives of this study and informed consent was secured to ensure that the participants understand what they are getting into. The following ethical concerns were also considered in determining the results of this study i.e., risk of harm, conflict of interest, honesty, and confidentiality (Data Privacy Act 2012). While handling the data, the researcher ensured confidentiality and avoided any forms of misleading information and conflict of interest. Before the commencement of this study, the researcher sought approval from Colegio de San Juan de Letran – Calamba. Also, a letter of intent was presented to Company Z to get their approval and the data needed for this research. The data collection, processing, and interpretation of results were facilitated by the researcher. Any gestures associated with subjectiveness and conflict of interest were not entertained to ensure the validity and integrity of the results.

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